

A Regenerative Photogalvanic Cell

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A regenerative photo-galvanic cell has been developed using anthraquinone-2-sulphonate (D) acting as a light absorber as well as an electron acceptor and triethanolamine (TEOA) as the electron donor. On illumination with visible light D abstracts electron from TEOA as in the equation,

Cyclic voltammetry shows that D/DH[•] couple is reversible at platinum and also at carbon electrode, while TEOA/TEOA⁺ is irreversible at platinum electrode but is electroactive at carbon electrode when it is impregnated with ruthenium. Using bright Pt electrode in the illuminated half-element and C-Ru as the dark electrode, an open-circuit potential of 700 mV is obtained. The current efficiency is low, ca 7.5 μA over a load of 1.8 k Ω, apparently due to polarisation at the Pt electrode (stirring increases the current). Cell with carbon in the illuminated-half and C-Ru in the dark-half element, has a higher current efficiency. The open-circuit potential is ca 620 mV; short circuit current is 0.7 mA. With illumination on, the cell yield a steady current of 50 μA over a load of 1.8 k Ω. The cell potential remains steady for about 72 h after the illumination is turned off. TEOA and D have been estimated and found to be constant after several charge-discharge cycles.

THE generation of electricity or high energy fuels from solar energy continues to attract attention as a viable alternative to meet the present energy crisis. Photogalvanic cell, a device for conversion of solar energy to electricity operates by the transfer of electrons between the species produced photochemically in the bulk of the solution and the electrode dipped into the solution. Among the few cells that have been so far developed, one with anthraquinone-2-sulphonate as light absorber (excited molecule acting as an electron acceptor) and sodium formate as electron donor was reported from this laboratory¹. Anthraquinone-2-sulphonate, in its excited state abstracts electron from formate² to produce semiquinolate ion, while the radical HCOO[•] produced from formate, reduces another molecule of D to give D^{•-} and CO₂,

In the cell, the net electrode reactions are, at illuminated electrodes D^{•-} → e + D, and at dark electrode, O₂ + e → O₂^{•-}. Formate acts as sacrificial electron donor and itself gets oxidised to CO₂ and thus the cell can also be termed as photogalvanic fuel cell. The open circuit potential of the cell at pH 10.5-11 is 500 mV and this open-circuit potential remains steady even 72 h after the illumination was off. A comparison of this cell with those previously studied is given in Table 1.

In the present paper, we report a regenerative photogalvanic cell using anthraquinone-2-sulphonate and triethanolamine.

TABLE 1—OPEN-CIRCUIT POTENTIAL, AND SHORT-CIRCUIT CURRENTS OF PHOTOGALVANIC CELLS

Sl. no.	Cell	Open-circuit potential mV	Short-circuit current μA
1.	Pt/Fe-thionine/Pt ^a	195	1.9
2.	SnO ₂ /Fe-thionine/Pt ^a	170	2.8
3.	TiO ₂ /Fe-thionine/Pt ^a	155	1.5
4.	TPP/Fe-thionine/Pt ^b	382	
5.	SnO ₂ /Rhodamine B/HQ/Au ^c	80	8.0
6.	Pt/Fe Poly(N-acrylamine methyl)thionine/Pt ^d	50	0.1
7.	Pt/AQ-formate/Pt ^e	500	250
8.	CdS/AQ-formate/Pt ^e	550	450

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Experimental

The cell has been described earlier¹. A 125 W Philips HPL mercury vapour lamp was used for illumination, emitting mainly in 400-440, 530-550 and 570-580 nm regions. Anthraquinone-2-sulphonate (B.D.H.) was used after recrystallisation. Triethanolamine hydrochloride (Sigma) and other chemicals were used as received. Carbon rods (40 mm × 8 mm dia.) were used as electrodes, after thorough cleaning by boiling in concentrated HNO₃, followed by repeated wash in boiled distilled water. Carbon rods, impregnated with Ru or Pt or their mixtures were prepared by electro-deposition from a solution of chloroplatinic acid and/or ruthe-

nium(III) chloride³. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded with a cyclic voltameter *cum* potentiostat fabricated in the laboratory using operational amplifiers. A three-electrode assembly with a platinum counter-electrode was employed and a standard calomel electrode was used as reference. A 0.1 M sodium sulphate solution was used as supporting electrolyte.

Triethanolamine was estimated spectrophotometrically at 560 nm by complexation with cobalt(II)⁴. Aliquots from the cell solution were taken time to time and mixed with alcoholic CoCl₂ solution in a buffer (pH 7.8) and concentration of TEOA calculated from the optical density at 560 nm (the absorption maxima of [Co(TEOA)₃]Cl₂).

Results and Discussion

Use of triethanolamine as donor instead of formate also showed photogalvanic effect. When a portion of the solution containing anthraquinone-2-sulphonate and triethanolamine were illuminated keeping the other part in dark and two platinum electrodes dipped in the two half-cells, a potential difference developed. At pH 10, the maximum steady potential attained on illumination was 550 mV, and short circuit current was 175 μA with bright platinum foil electrodes. With carbon impregnated with Ru and Pt as dark electrode in the cell at pH 10, the potential remained at 530 mV. The steady current is 112 μA over a load of 1.8 kΩ (meter resistance). After drawing current for about 40 h without illumination the current goes down to 15 μA. On illumination the potential again rises to 520 mV. Similar charge-discharge was repeated for at least five times. When carbon rods itself were used as both the electrodes, the maximum potential attained was only 180 mV. Using carbon, impregnated with Ru and Pt as dark electrode and carbon as illuminated one, the steady potential did not exceed 200 mV. The cell was studied at different pH's. In neutral and slightly acidic media, with illumination the open circuit potential rose to the steady value of 500 mV. However, the current was much lower compared to that at pH 10, the steady current being only 7 μA with bright platinum foil electrodes. At high pH's (pH > 11), the steady potential reached a value of

725 mV, the time required to attain this value is also lower and the current is high. With carbon impregnated with Ru and Pt as dark electrode and platinum foil as illuminated one, the steady current is 50 μA over a load of 1.8 kΩ. But the difficulty with this alkaline cell is that after discharge, when the cell was again illuminated, the potential rises to only 560 mV, and pH of the solution after discharge gets lowered. But as the pH was raised by adding some alkali, the potential again rose to 725 mV. Similar phenomena were observed on further charge discharge processes. The above observation may be explained in terms of the acid-base equilibrium of triethanolamine cation (TEOA⁺), which is produced in the cell as

At pH 9 and higher, the cation deprotonates to yield a neutral radical with the unpaired electron in α-position to either the amino or alcohol group.

While in acid and neutral media the cation radical TEOA⁺ is stable, the deprotonated species shows a reducing properties and as a result it probably reduces another ground state D molecule as

Thus, at higher pH's the rate of formation of D^{·-} is almost double than that in acid and neutral medium. The above reaction also explains why after every cycle of charging in alkaline medium, the pH of the solution gets lowered.

As the triethanolamine cation TEOA⁺ is stable in acid medium this may be electro-active. So we attempted to develop a regenerative photogalvanic cell. In this cell the passage of oxygen in the dark chamber was not allowed and using various electrode combination the potential was measured with respect to a standard calomel electrode, immersed in the cell. Table 2 shows the values

TABLE 2—POTENTIALS OF PHOTOGALVANIC CELL, | D, TEOA | WITH DIFFERENT ELECTRODES
ill. dark

D = 2.5 × 10⁻³ M, TEOA = 5 × 10⁻¹ M, pH = 2-3.

Illuminated-half		Dark-half		Potential difference (mV) (O.C.P. of cell)
Electrode	Potential (mV) vs SCE	Electrode	Potential (mV) vs SCE	
Bright Pt	-(400-420)	Platinised Pt	-(340-380)	+ 60
Bright Pt	- 400	Carbon	80	+480
Bright Pt	-(400-420)	Carbon with Ru	(300-260)	+700
Carbon	- 360	Carbon with Ru × Pt	100	+470
Carbon with Pt	- 360	Carbon with Ru	210	+570
Carbon	- 300	Carbon with Ru	320	+620

of open-circuit potential of such cell and also the potential of individual electrode with respect to SCE using various electrode combinations.

The E value for $D/D^{\cdot-}$ at the above pH is 400 mV (*vs* SCE). With carbon electrode in the illuminated-half the potential of -300 mV compared to -400 mV with bright platinum is probably due to the reason that both $D^{\cdot-}$ and $TEOA^{\cdot+}$ acts at the carbon electrode while only $D/D^{\cdot-}$ is electroactive at platinum. Impregnation of Ru in carbon however helps the cation to act more reversibly at the electrode thus making the dark electrode potential more positive, e.g. (300-280) mV compared to that with platinum or carbon. When carbon impregnated with both Ru and Pt, is used in the dark chamber the potential changes to a lower value ca 110 mV *vs* SCE and when only platinum foil is used in that half the potential becomes negative, ca -350 mV thus decreasing the open circuit potential. The maximum open-circuit potential is obtained by using platinum in the illuminated-half and carbon impregnated with Ru electrode in the dark-half. It has also been observed that after the illumination was off when the cell was kept in dark, the potential of the dark electrode slowly becomes more positive, probably due to slow diffusion of triethanolamine cation to the electrode.

For the regenerative cell with bright platinum as the illuminated electrode and carbon impregnated with Ru as dark electrode (open-circuit potential 725 mV) the short-circuit current is only 120 μ A and within 100 min the current falls down to 7.5 μ A. The potential of each electrode is measured with respect to SCE under closed circuit condition; the values are, dark electrode, -305 mV *vs* SCE, and illuminated Pt electrode, -265 mV *vs* SCE. Comparison of these values with the open-circuit condition indicates high polarisation at the platinum. After drawing current for some time when the circuit is made open, the open circuit potential as well as the potential of the illuminated platinum electrode slowly rises to the previous value. For the cell with carbon as illuminated electrode and carbon impregnated with Ru as dark one, the short-circuit current is 0.7 mA (c.c.p. 375 mV) steady current 50 μ A, with illumination on. The current is drawn for eight hours over load of 1.8 k Ω when the value remains steady at 50 μ A (c.c.p. 90 mV).

Cyclic voltammetry of 1.5×10^{-3} M solution of AQS in presence of 0.5 M Na_2SO_4 was carried out using platinum electrode under both oxygen and nitrogen medium. The voltammogram is shown in Fig. 1. Under N_2 with scan rate of 1.8 Vs^{-1} the cathodic peak at -0.53 V and the anodic peak at -0.43 V *vs* SCE is due to the redox couple AQS/AQSH $^{\cdot}$. The separation of the cathodic and anodic peaks at different scan rates obeys the relation,

$$E_{Pa} - E_{Pc} = \frac{0.058}{n} V$$

(where, E_{Pa} and E_{Pc} are the anodic and cathodic peak voltages and V the scan rate in Vs^{-1})

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammetry of anthraquinone-2-sulphonate (1.5×10^{-3} M) in presence of 0.5 M Na_2SO_4 , with Pt-electrode scan rate (1) 1.8 and (2) 1.2 Vs^{-1} : (—) in presence of O_2 , and (---) in absence of O_2 .

suggesting that the system is truly reversible at platinum.

In the AQS/triethanolamine cell, the observed open-circuit potential of the illuminated platinum electrode is -0.400 to -0.420 V. The CV anodic peak is -0.43 V (*vs* SCE). This indicates that the potential of illuminated Pt electrode is mainly controlled by the AQS/AQSH $^{\cdot}$ system. In presence of oxygen the cathodic peak at -0.075 V is due to reduction of oxygen. In the cell, when oxygen is allowed in the dark chamber, the dark electrode potential is controlled by $O_2/O_2^{\cdot-}$ system. In absence of oxygen, with platinum electrode in both chambers, the potential of the dark electrode (-0.34 - 0.38 V) indicates that AQS/AQH $^{\cdot}$ controls the dark electrode potential too and hence no photopotential is observed.

Cyclic voltammetry of anthraquinone-2-sulphonate with carbon electrode (Fig. 2) showed a greater separation between the cathodic and anodic peak, the latter being shifted to more positive value,

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammetry of anthraquinone-2-sulphonate (2.5×10^{-3} M) in presence of 0.5 M Na_2SO_4 , with carbon electrode.

namely, -0.1 V vs SCE. CV has also been recorded with triethanolamine solution using Pt-deposited carbon as well as Ru-deposited carbon electrodes (Fig. 3). No sharp cathodic peak is observed with carbon impregnated with Pt, while the cathodic peak at $+0.3$ V vs SCE observed with Ru-deposited

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammetry of triethanolamine (0.05 M) in presence of 0.5 M Na_2SO_4 , with (—) Pt-deposited C electrode, and (---) Ru-deposited C electrode.

carbon is probably due to the reduction of the cation TEOA^+ formed in the anodic half.

In the cell, using Ru-deposited carbon electrode in the dark-half, the open-circuit potential of 0.28–0.3 V vs SCE, is the potential at which TEOA^+ is reduced and DH^+ is oxidised at equal rates. Further, to justify that triethanolamine is not irreversibly oxidised (or consumed) in the cell, it has been estimated after each charge-discharge cycle and it is found to be constant upto at least five cycles.

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